

Sexual harassment attitude among selected Psychology undergraduates of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria: Does educational intervention make a difference?

***Opeyemi Oyewunmi, Ekundayo**

Department of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

opewunmi@gmail.com; ekundayoo@oauife.edu.ng

+234 703 786 1275

Monica, Fedeli

Department of Philosophy, Sociology, Pedagogy and Applied Psychology, University of Padova, Italy.

monica.fedeli@unipd.it

+39 049 8271713

*Corresponding author

Funders: Coimbra scholarship

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8256322](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8256322)

Abstract

Sexual harassment has been a major issue in Nigeria, especially in the University system. The introduction of #MeToo movement has raised the awareness of sexual harassment and its psychological effects to a higher level. Sexual harassment has serious implications for students and staff psychological well-being as well as on university image. This paper investigates the gender difference in the attitude of students to sexual

harassment. The study further seeks to explore the impact of educational intervention on the sexual harassment attitudes of undergraduates.

An ex post facto research design was used to explore the attitude of student's sexual harassment. A pre-test and post-test were conducted to examine student's sexual harassment. The sample consisted of eighty-seven participants who were Psychology part three students who registered for the Human Sexuality course. Thirty-six were males and fifty-one were females with ages ranging between 20 years and 27 years. The sexual harassment attitude scale was administered to the students at the first contact of the class to elicit baseline responses from respondents. This class was educated on sexual harassment at every contact of 12 weeks for 15 minutes. The educational intervention employed an anecdotal method using vignettes involving sexual harassment cases and examples as presented to participants for projection of attribution and suggestion of appropriate sanctions. The vignettes depicted scenes of classroom sexual harassment ranging from unwelcomed and sexist compliments to unwanted physical contact. The post-test was done after the last contact class.

The analysis of the result showed that there is a gender difference in the sexual harassment attitude of respondents where males have more positive sexual harassment attitude. There was also a slight difference between the sexual harassment attitude of respondents pre and post intervention

Keywords: *Sexual harassment, educational intervention, Attitude, Undergraduates, young adults.*

Introduction

Sexual harassment is an unsolicited, unwelcome, and unreciprocated sexual overture from a person to elicit unwanted sexual relations from another person (OAU Anti-sexual harassment policy, 2013). Unreciprocated sexual overtures such as physical, verbal, or non-verbal and may involve but is not limited to assault, bullying, coercion, discrimination, favoritism (of a sexual nature), exploitation, intimidation, inappropriate or the unwelcome promise of rewards of any kind in exchange for sexual favors (OAU Anti sexual harassment policy, 2013).

Sexual harassment is a concern because it could cause psychological pain annoying, humiliating, intimidating, offensive, frustrating, stressful, and embarrassing (Burn, 2019; Langer, 2017), and sometimes physical health

crises to the victim thereby hindering productivity. Even though the menace occurs in different settings and affects diverse persons including teachers, students, employers, and employees, young and old, male, and female, yet one would expect a more civilized setting in the university as it is the citadel of learning and enlightenment for the society at large. The university system in which faculty members for some good reasons are entrusted with a substantial level of trust (*loco parentis*), and authority in their teaching relationship with students, are disappointingly involved in this social phenomenon and concern called sexual harassment (Adeniyi, 2020).

During the #MeToo movement, people called out their perpetrators of sexual harassment across the globe. Sexual harassment became an issue of great magnitude with louder voices across organizations, institutions, and the globe (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020; Idris et al, 2016). Several incidences of sexual harassment have been documented across African and Nigerian Universities. For instance, in Ethiopia, the prevalence rate of physical, verbal, and non-verbal sexual harassment is 22.1%, 38.4%, and 17.1% respectively (Tegegne, Tegegne & Tesemma, 2019) and 50% of all females have experienced at least a form of sexual harassment (Tora, 2013). At the University of Malawi, Ogbonnaya and Emma-Echiegu (2017) reported a prevalence rate of 67% sexual harassment among the students. In Ghana and Tanzania, some male lecturers consider sex from students in exchange for grades as their rights (Morley, 2011). At Obafemi Awolowo University Nigeria, in 2018, a professor was found guilty, dismissed, and jailed for sexual harassment (Sahara Reporters, 2018) and another lecturer was also sacked at Cairo University, Egypt for sexual harassment in July 2019. In a similar vein, Eze (2020) reported that two lecturers at Imo State University, Nigeria were suspended for sexual harassment.

Thus, Nigerian tertiary institutions have recorded a very high prevalence of sexual harassment with differences across female and male gender (Anierobi, Etodike, Nwogbo, Okeke, & Nwikpo, 2021; Adeniyi, 2020; Eze, 2020; Moughalu & Olaoye, 2016; Omonijo et al, 2013). This nature of prevalence might be because of the skewed power dynamics between the gender that is entrenched in our patriarchal culture (Moughalu et al, 2016), and reportedly higher in developing countries as a result of weak accountability mechanisms, low funding, and lack or low gender mainstreaming (Lynch, 2013) with little or no sexual harassment training for both lecturers and students. Sexual harassment is also more prevalent among university staff when they are poorly remunerated, rarely, or

poorly trained, and under-sourced (Beninger, 2013). In 2020, Okondu, Afolabi, Ikonta, and Iloma argued that even though the awareness and knowledge of sexual harassment among college students in Nigeria are good, the prevalence of sexual harassment remains high.

Recently, Nigerian lawmakers approved a bill to protect students from sexual harassment in the nation's tertiary institutions (Anadolu, 2020) and most Nigerian universities including Obafemi Awolowo University have an existing anti-sexual harassment policy or zero tolerance for sexual harassment, yet sexual harassment is continually on the increase as reported in previous studies. Such previous studies have focused on prevalence and consequences of sexual harassment, but few studies have focused on educational intervention among students as a form of empowerment to reduce and/or prevent future occurrences. It is therefore imperative to empower students through some educational training on sexual harassment (Omonijo, Dare & Ojo, 2013; Joseph, 2015; Suleiman, 2017; Anene & Osayamwen, 2019; Olaigbe & Fagbenro, 2021).

While raising the following questions: to what extent have the vignettes created exposed the attitude of students towards sexual harassment? Are there gender differences in the interpretations of these created scenarios on sexual harassment? It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate the attitude of students to sexual harassment, and to explore if an educational intervention on the sexual harassment change the attitudes of undergraduates. This educational training was aims to engage students through discussions and work in pairs and in group through the learning using vignettes and images.

Objectives of the study

The study seeks to

1. Examine the gender differences in sexual harassment attitude among undergraduates of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife
2. Determine if an educational intervention on the sexual harassment attitude of undergraduates of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife have an influence on their attitudes in terms of change behaviour.

Theoretical framework

Theory of planned behaviour

The primary aim of this study is to determine whether the educational intervention employed to change the knowledge level and attitude of psychology students towards sexual harassment was effective. The theory of planned behaviour is a cognitive-affective theory of social psychology

developed to predict and explain the psychological determinants of human behaviour within a specific context (Ajzen, 2002). It focuses on the attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control of human behaviour. Attitude according to this theory is a learned predisposition to act in a consistently favourable or unfavourable manner towards an object or subject. That is, students, lecturers and administrative staff can condone sexual harassment and accept victim-blaming without being aware of their favourable attitude. The subjective norm speaks to an individual's perception of social pressure to perform or not to perform a behaviour. When the perceived norm from society negates the sexual harassment, the individual is likely to seek change or report the sexual assault. Perceived behavioural control reflects individual past experiences as related to future obstacles and impediments; it is the perceived ease or difficulty of performing a behaviour and the sense of control an individual feels they have over such behaviour.

The theory of planned behavior can guide the development of sexual harassment prevention programs. The theory suggests that if attitudes were important determinants of intentions, then interventions for that population should be directed at changing attitudes toward such behaviour, which is sexual harassment in this case. In the same vein, if subjective norms were more important, it would be important to design intervention programmes that would change perceived norms regarding sexual harassment in universities. Likewise, if perceived behavior control were the most important, then intervention activities might be directed toward building skills such as assertiveness and communication. This study focuses on examining whether educational intervention programmes would change the attitude of Psychology Students towards sexual harassment. An active learning approach was used to design the training. Active learning is an intentional process that must be well-projected and planned to be effective. A teacher who uses an active approach is a facilitator (Fedeli, 2016; Fedeli & Taylor, 2016), promoting change and designing learning in collaboration with students to create an authentic and engaging climate. Research confirms that active learning can be implemented across different disciplines and contexts and that it is transformative and long-term (Felder & Brent, 2016). Active learning (AL) involves new approaches on the part of teachers as well as new awareness and involvement on the part of students. AL promotes student participation in the performance of learning activities by encouraging students to think actively about what they are doing (Bonwell & Eison,

1991). While in principle this definition could include traditional tasks, AL refers to activities that also take place in the classroom and thus require a different teaching style. AL can be explained through the "seven principles for good practice" by Chickering & Gamson, (1987):

- encourage contact between students and faculty;
- develop reciprocity and cooperation among students;
- encourage active learning;
- give timely feedback;
- emphasize time on task;
- communicate high expectations;
- respect different talents and ways of learning.

The work of Prince, (2004) also recognized three forms of AL: collaborative learning, cooperative learning, and problem-based learning. Some research states that AL increases student performance, has a significant impact on the quality of learning. In addition, students learn better in groups than in solitude (Freeman, Eddy, Mc Dounough et al., 2014; Michael, 2006).

Based on this approach all the training sessions were interactive, encouraging students to confront, discuss and compare their perspectives, using vignettes and images, and taking responsibility of their learning process and behavior.

Materials and Methods

The ex-post facto research design was used to examine sexual harassment attitude among psychology year-three students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Asika (1991) explains that ex-post facto research design observes events that have indeed taken place to evaluate such events without manipulation. Eighty-seven students (51 females and 37 males) with ages ranging between 20 years and 27 years with a standard deviation of 1.912 and a mean of 21.63 years were involved in the study. The participants were year-three psychology students who registered for the Human Sexuality class A pre-test and post-test were conducted to examine the influence of educational intervention on student's sexual harassment attitudes. A pre-test was conducted at the beginning of the class to form the baseline of sexual harassment attitude of the student within the class. For a semester, a maximum of 30 minutes each week during the two-hour class period was allocated to discussions about sexual harassment (12 weeks of classes). The post-test was done on the last contact class.

The scenario questionnaire administered to the respondents consisted of 36 items. These questions were based on hypothetical scenarios to debrief students on the perception and attitude towards sexual harassment among year-three Psychology students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. Respondents were presented with scenarios that connote possible sexual harassment between the lecturer and his students. Each of the items on the questionnaire presented for judgment by the students a description of sexual harassment as initiated by a lecturer. The questionnaire was administered as in-class activity by the lecturer at the first and last contact as the class was supposed to learn about sexual harassment as part of their course content.

Participants were given consent forms to sign. They were assured of confidentiality and anonymity.

The intervention

The intervention programme was incorporated into the weekly classes of year-three psychology students who registered for 'Human Sexuality'. Within the two-hour class period, a maximum of 30 minutes per week was dedicated to the discussions around sexual harassment for a semester (12 weeks of classes). The study took place between April and July 2019. The intervention was developed by the researcher to expose the understanding and attitude of students toward sexual harassment with vivid examples and vignettes. The educational intervention employed an active learning approach and an anecdotal method, using images, vignettes involving sexual harassment cases and examples as presented to participants for projection of attribution and suggestion of appropriate sanctions. The vignettes depicted scenes of classroom sexual harassment ranging from unwelcomed and sexist compliments to unwanted physical contact. The intervention was specifically structured in a way that the class begins with the explanation of definitions and forms of sexual harassment while students' reactions were expressed and discussed. After which the teacher, guides the class based on the sexual harassment policy of the university. All the sessions happened in the first half-hour of the class. Students disclosed that they were always looking forward to the class because of their engagement thanks to the active learning approach adopted by the teacher.

The intervention programme was developed by the researcher to include the definitions of sexual harassment, types of sexual harassment, situations in which sexual harassment occurs by vignettes, and expected

reactions of students toward sexual harassment based on the anti-sexual harassment policy of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria.

Table 1: The educational intervention programme based on OAU anti-sexual harassment policy

General purposes	Title of the session	Activities	Time
Introductory class (introduction of students to each other and the purpose of the class).	Introduction to the study	Written consent is given by the participants, and a pre-test was conducted	15 minutes
Familiarizing the individuals with the different available definitions of sexual harassment	Definition of sexual harassment	Expressing individual feelings and thoughts on these definitions	15minutes 2 classes
Determining the advantages and disadvantages of sexual harassment in lecturer-student relationships by students	Scenarios of sexual harassment	Class discussion Questions and answers	15 minutes 3 classes
Expression of individual feelings and thoughts on sexual harassment	Situations in which sexual harassment occurs	Reactions and class discussion; questions and answers	15 minutes 3classes

Expression of individual fears and concerns about possible sexual harassment	Situations in which sexual harassment occurs	Reactions and class discussion; questions and answers	15 minutes 3classes
--	--	---	------------------------

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS statistics 23. Results were statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. There were no missing values since it was a small group of young adults who were committed to this course of study. The study conducted a test of the difference between the pre-educational intervention and post-educational intervention periods.

Results

The result shows that there are gender differences in participant’s attitude towards sexual harassment with higher number of male and female participants having negative attitude towards sexual harassment. The mean differences were found to be significant.

Table 2a

Independent sample t-test with gender and sexual harassment attitude

	Phase I						Phase II					
	N	Mea	SD	t	d	Sig	N	Mea	SD	t	d	Sig
	n			f		.	n			f		.
Male	3	130.1	9.915	.82	8	.411	3	125.1	8.09	.94	8	.34
	6	7		7	5		6	7	1	4	5	8
Female	51	128.2	10.91				51	122.9	12.10			
	7	8					8	7				

As a test of the hypothesis that gender differential will significantly influence the sexual harassment attitudes of undergraduates. In order to compare scores between males and females on sexual harassment attitude, an independent t-test was conducted. This test was found to be statistically not significant $t(85) = .827, p > .05$ in phase I and $t(85) = .944, p > .348$ in phase II. These results further indicate that males ($\chi = 130.17, SD = 9.915$) have a more positive sexual harassment attitude than females ($\chi = 128.27, SD = 10.918$) undergraduates in Phase I with the same higher positive

attitude among males ($\chi = 125.17$, $SD = 8.091$) than females ($\chi = 122.98$, $SD = 12.107$) undergraduates.

Table 2b

Independent sample t-test with gender on sexual harassment attitude in Phase I and II

		Phase I					Phase II						
	SHA	N	Mean	S.D	t	Df	Sig.	N	Mean	S.D	t	df	Sig.
Male	Negative	30	127.37	8.19	-	34	.000	32	123.47	6.67	-	34	.000
	Positive	6	144.17	4.12	4.862			4	138.75	5.25	4.396		
Female	Negative	44	125.05	7.58	-	49	.000	45	119.76	7.99	-	49	.000
	Positive	7	148.57	4.99	7.910			6	147.17	10.42	7.626		

Cut off point for positive/negative attitude is the mean with one standard deviation that is $130.17 \pm 9.915 = 120$ for positive, 140 for negative in phase I $125.17 \pm 8.091 = 117$ for positive, 133 for negative in phase II

To further test the gender differences in participants' sexual harassment attitude, the study compared scores between the males and females on sexual harassment attitude with an independent sample t-test. This test was found to be statistically significant. The mean differences at post intervention phase were found to be significant among males ($\chi = 123.4$, $SD = 6.67$); $t(34) = -4.396$, $p < .005$) and females ($\chi = 119.76$, $SD = 7.98$); $t(49) = -7.626$, $p < .005$).

To test the difference between the pre-intervention and the post-intervention groups, means, and standard deviations were computed on the scores of the 87 participants on the measures of sexual harassment attitudes. The results are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3

Results of test of difference between scores of pre-intervention and post-intervention on sexual harassment attitudes

	Phase I	Phase II
--	---------	----------

Measures	Mean	S.D	Mean
<u>S.D</u>			
Scenario 1a 3.55	16.24	3.87	15.61
Scenario 1b 3.29	16.78	2.99	15.74
Scenario 1c 0.85	16.57	1.33	8.56
Scenario 2a 3.76	15.62	3.68	14.63
Scenario 2b 3.77	16.87	3.66	16.20
Scenario 2c 2.17	16.44	1.52	11.41
Scenario 1 10.38	84.10	9.94	79.45
Scenario 2 2.77	44.95	2.75	44.44

The results presented in Table 3 revealed that the opinion of the respondents in phase I (M = 84.10; SD = 9.94) and its subscales had slightly higher mean scenario scores than phase II (M = 79.45; SD = 10.38) and its subscales for scenario I. The result also revealed that respondents when exposed to the second scenario before (M= 44.95; SD = 2.75) and after (M = 44.44; SD = 2.77) intervention had a slight difference in their sexual harassment attitude. To determine if the observed mean differences in Table 3 are statistically significant, Paired-Samples t-Test was used to compare the scores for the two phases. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Paired-samples t-test between phases on sexual harassment attitudes

Measures		Mean	SD	t	df	Sig
Verbal harassment by professor with threats/rewards	Scenario 1a PhaseI Scenario 1a PhaseII	.632	4.868	1.211	86	.229
Action(s) taken by student	Scenario 1b PhaseI Scenario 1b PhaseII	1.046	4.123	2.366	86	.020
Student's feelings	Scenario 1c PhaseI Scenario 1c PhaseII	8.011	1.610	46.407	86	.000
Physical harassment by professor with threats/rewards	Scenario 2a PhaseI Scenario 2a PhaseII	.989	5.531	1.667	86	.099
Action(s) taken by student	Scenario 2b PhaseI Scenario 2b Phase II	.678	4.833	1.309	86	.194

Students' feelings	Scenario 2c	5.02	2.715	17.25	86	.00
	Phase I	3		6		0
	Scenario 2c					
	Phase II					

A paired samples t-test was performed to compare the difference between pre intervention sexual harassment attitude and post intervention. The results presented in Table 4 revealed that there was a partial statistical significant difference in student’s reaction towards verbal harassment with threat/reward between pre-educational intervention (M = 16.78, SD = 2.99) and post-educational intervention (M = 15.74, SD = 3.29); $t(86) = 2.366$, $p = 0.020$. Also, there was a significant difference between how students felt about being sexually harassed by the professor pre-educational intervention (M = 16.57, SD = 1.33) and post-education intervention (M = 8.56, SD = 0.85); $t(86) = 46.4$, $p = .000$ in scenario I. In scenario II, there was also a significant difference in student’s reaction towards physical harassment by the professor between pre-educational intervention (M = 16.44, SD = 1.52) and post-educational intervention (M = 11.41, SD = 2.17); $t(86) = 17.3$, $p = .000$.

Discussion of findings

The study sought to better understand the preventive measures that can be taken by stakeholders on sexual harassment victimization in educational setting in Nigeria by examining the responses of respondents to some hypothetical sexual scenarios before and after sexual harassment educational trainings. The study evaluated the responses of 87 year- three psychology students who registered for ‘Human sexuality’ class to sexual harassment. Sexual harassment educational training is associated with a broader definition of what constitutes sexual harassment.

The majority of the respondents in this survey had a rather high level of awareness about sexual harassment, which was reflected in their attitudes with females having a more negative attitude towards sexual harassment than male respondents. This could be due to the fact that females are more likely to be victims of sexual harassment than males, and/or because males are often bystanders or spectators in incidents of sexual harassment. The positive attitude of males toward sexual harassment could also be as a result of a subjective norm that perceives a subtle acceptance of sexual

dominance towards female. Men seem to be less aware of existing power differentials related to gender, according to sociocultural reality, because they are accustomed to living in a society with a gender hierarchy that advantages them. Given that men and women have distinct perspectives due to their diverse perspectives and experiences with power in society, it is not surprising that gender had a significant impact on the sexual harassment attitude of respondent pre- and post-intervention.

This result is in sync with previous research reporting gender difference in the attitude and perception of sexual harassment (Mohipp & Senn, 2008; Moughalu & Olaoye, 2016). Mohipp and Senn opined that female were less tolerant of sexual harassment and more supportive of feminism than males, according to their analysis of opinions. They concluded that gender attitudes matter because they promote the idea that men and women have different experiences in our society, making women more aware of and sensitive to unequal conditions.

The study anticipated that there will be a significant difference between the sexual harassment attitude based on the hypothetical scenarios of respondents before and after educational intervention. This hypothesis received support as there was a slight difference between the sexual harassment attitude of respondents pre and post intervention. The possible explanation for this difference is the impact the training had on the sexual harassment attitude of respondent. According to Bingham and Scherer's (2001) study of sexual harassment training in universities can help workers become more sensitive to the problem of workplace sexual harassment. Also, individual training appears to be more effective in clarifying men's attitudes toward inappropriate sexual behaviour perpetrated by employees rather than bosses as suggested by Antecol and Cobb-Clark (2003).

There appears to be some differences in the significance of educational training based on the two of the three components of the vignette which are 'student's feelings towards the harassment scenario' and 'students' action and reactions towards handling the harassment'.

Conclusion

Sexual harassment training is associated with a broader definition of what constitutes sexual harassment. If they have received training, both males and females are more likely to say that unwelcome sexual gestures, statements, deliberate touching, and pressure for dates are kinds of sexual harassment. Individual students' predisposition to perceive various sorts of unwanted sexual advances as sexual harassment is positively related after they received training. It is therefore recommended that verbal and

non-verbal sexual harassment can be controlled with adequate and diverse trainings such as communication, educational, and assertiveness training.

Limitation of study

Further research of sexual harassment should be undertaken in a more naturalistic context wherever possible to allow results to be more widely generalized. Future research should also integrate a personal history measure, which could help identify the potential interaction between previous experiences and sexual harassment exposure and educational therapy approaches.

A more enlightened educational culture appears to be aided by extensive sexual harassment training for students, lecturers and administrative staff is recommendation.

Declaration of Conflict of interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors

Funding

This project was supported by the Coimbra group scholarship for young Sub-Saharan African scholars.

References

Adeniyi, O. (2020). *Naked Abuse: Sex for grades in African Universities*. (first Ed.) ThisDaybooks, Lagos

Aina-Pelemo, A.D. & Ejembi, P.A. (2020). *Sexual Harassment and the Law* (first (Ed.), Jos University Press, Jos

Ajzen, I. (2002). Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control. And the theory of planned behaviour. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(4), 665-683.

Anadolu Agency 2020. "Nigeria moves to shield students from sexual harassment: senate passes bill to protect students in country's institutes of higher education" (Anadolu Agency), available at:

<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/africa/nigeria-moves-to-shield-students-from-sexual-harassment/1903537#> (last accessed 15th June 2021).

- Anene & Osayamwen (2019). Clear and Present Danger! Quid-Pro-Quo Sexual Harassment as a Limitation to Female Access to Quality Tertiary Education in South-West Nigeria
- Anierobi, E. I., Etodike, C. E., Nwogbo, V. N., Okeke, N. U., & Nwikpo, M. N. (2021). Evaluating Sexual Harassment against Female Workers in Higher Institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(2), 265–278.
- Antecol, H. & Cobb-Clark, D. A. (2003). “Does Sexual Harassment Training Change Attitudes? A View from the Federal Level”, *Social Science Quarterly*, 84 (4), 826-842.
- Beninger, C. (2013). Combating Sexual Harassment in Schools in Sub-Saharan Africa: Legal Strategies Under Regional and International Human Rights Law. *African Human Rights Law Journal*, 13, 281-301
- Bondestam, F. & Lundqvist, M. (2020) Sexual harassment in higher education – a systematic review, *European Journal of Higher Education*, 10(4), 397-419, DOI: [10.1080/21568235.2020.1729833](https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2020.1729833)
- Bonwell, C. C., & J. A. Eison. (1991). Active learning: Creating excitement in the classroom. *ASHE-ERIC Higher Education Report No. 1*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press.
- Burn, S. M. (2019). The Psychology of Sexual Harassment. *Teaching of Psychology*, 46(1), 96–103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0098628318816183>
- Chickering, A.W., Gamson, Z. (fall 1987). Seven principles for good practices in undergraduate education. *Washington Center News*. 1-7.
- Ejembi, A.P., Aina-Pelemo, A.D., Ejembi, O. J. & Aina, I.T. (2020). The trajectory of Nigerian law regarding sexual harassment in the workplace. *African Journal of Law Human Rights*, 4 (2), 1-9.
- Erinosho, S., Femi-Oyewo, M. N., & Oduwole, E. (2018). Sexual harassment on campus: A study in a Nigeria University. *AGOGO: Journal of Humanities*, 4, 1-10.
- Eze, J., 2020. IMSU suspends lecturers involved in alleged sex-for-grade Scandal (Premium times), available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com> (last accessed 4th June 2021).

- Fedeli, M. (2016). Coinvolgere gli studenti nelle pratiche didattiche: potere, dialogo e partecipazione. M. Fedeli, V. Grion, & D. Frison (Eds.), *Coinvolgere per apprendere. Metodi e tecniche partecipative per la formazione* (pp.113-142). Lecce: Pensa Multimedia.
- Fedeli, M., & Taylor, E.W. (2016). Exploring the impact of a teacher study group in an Italian university. *Formazione & Insegnamento*, XIV (3), 2279- 7505.
- Felder, R.M., & Brent, R. (2016). *Teaching and learning STEM. A practical guide*. San Francisco (CA): Jossey Bass.
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *PNAS Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111, 8410–8415. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1319030111>
- Idris, H., Adaja, J., Audu, S., & Aye, G. A. (2016). Analysis of the causes and effects of sexual harassment on the performance of female employees in some selected organizations in Kogi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Democratic and Development Studies*, 2 (2), 31-39
- Jemmott, J.B., Jemmott, L.S., Hines, P.M., et al (2001). The Theory of Planned Behavior as a Model of Intentions for Fighting Among African American and Latino Adolescents. *Maternal Child Health Journal*, 5, 253–263 <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013032906379>
- Joseph, J (2015). Sexual harassment in tertiary institutions: a comparative perspective. *Temida* 18(2), 125-144
- Kara, D., & Toygar, S. A. (2019). Gender Differences in Attitudes Toward Sexual Harassment of Health Care Employees: A Turkish Case Study. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 34(17), 3574–3591. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518815711>
- Langer, G. (2017, October 17). Unwanted sexual advances not just a Hollywood, Weinstein story, poll finds. Retrieved from <https://abcnews.go.com/Politics/unwanted-sexual-advances-hollywood-weinstein-story-poll/story?id=50521721>
- Leach, F. (2013) Corruption as Abuse of Power: Sexual Violence in Educational Institutions. In: G. Sweeney, K. Despota, S. Lindner (EOS). Transparency International, Global Corruption Report: Education. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, pp. 88-98.

- Michael, J. (2006). Where's the evidence that active learning works? *Advances in Physiology Education*, 30, 159-167. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1152/advan.00053.2006>
- Mohipp, C., & Senn, C. Y. (2008). Graduate students' perceptions of contrapower sexual harassment. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 23(9), 1258-1276. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260508314299>
- Morley, L. (2011). Sex, grades and power in higher education in Ghana and Tanzania. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 41(1), 101-115.
- Moughalu C. O. & Olaoye R. I. (2016). Perception of sexual harassment among students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*. 14(2), 140-152.
- Okondu, O. E., Afolabi, A.R, Ikonta, P. C., & Iloma, U. R (2020). Prevalence of sexual harassment in a faith-based institution of Higher learning in South-Western Nigeria. *Global journal of health science*, 12 (13), 1-1. DOI:[10.5539/gjhs.v12n13p1](https://doi.org/10.5539/gjhs.v12n13p1)
- Olaigbe, T. A & Fagbenro, D. A. (2021). Fighting female sexual harassment in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. *Journal of International cooperation and development* 4(1), 103-103.
- Omonijo, D. O., Uche, O. C. O., Nwadiofor, K. L., Rotimi, O. A. (2013). A study of sexual harassment in three selected private faith-based universities, Ogun State, South-West Nigeria. *Open Journal of Social Science Research*, 9, 250-263.
- Prince, M. (2004). Does active learning work? A review of the research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93223-23.
- Shivaraju, P. T., Manu, G., Vinaya, M, & Savkar, M. K. (2017). Evaluating the effectiveness of a pre-and post-test model of learning in a medical school. *National Journal of Physiology and Pharm Pharmacology*, 7(9), 947-951.
- Stroem, I. F., Goodman, K. L., Ybarra, M. L., & Mitchell, K. J. (2021). Understanding Sexual Harassment Through an Individual and Relational Lens: Are Risk Factors the Same for Female and Male Perpetrators? *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 8862605211028316. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08862605211028316>
- Suleiman, M. S. (2017). Perception of sexual harassment among female students of tertiary institutions in Northern Nigeria. *Ifè Social Sciences Review*, 25(2), 80-89
- Tesfaye Tegegne, K., Tegegne, E. T., & Tesemma, M. K. (2019). Prevalence of Sexual Harassments and Their Association with Psychological Distress among Pharma College Female Students,

Southern, Ethiopia; 2018. *Journal of Medical Care Research and Review*, 2(3), 101-119. <https://doi.org/10.15520/mcrr.v2i3.23>

Tora A. (2013). Assessment of sexual violence against female students in Wolaita Sodo University, Southern Ethiopia. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 28(11), 2351-2367. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260512475316>.